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ANDROID-BASED CONTEXTUALIZED ELECTRONIC STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS (ACE-SIMS) ON THE SELECTED TOPICS IN EARTH SCIENCE

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TEACHER I

DALIG NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
ANTIPOLO CITY

An Action Research Paper

Presented to Schools Division Research Committee (SDRC)

City Schools Division Office of Antipolo

ABSTRACT

The study focused on the acceptability and effectiveness of the developed android-based Contextualized Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (ACE-SIMS) on the Selected Topics in Earth Science. The study was conducted at Dalig National High School, to 56 purposely selected Grade 9 Learners during the third quarter of the School Year 2022-2023.

The study used quasi-experimental research method. The teacher-validators rated the ACE-SIMS as "very acceptable" in all the given criteria. Afterward, the selected Grade 9 learners were divided into two groups. The higher increase in the mean score of the ACE-SIMS group versus the non-ACE-SIMS group suggests that the developed ACE-SIMS has greatly improved learners' academic performance. In both groups, learners' performance on the pretest was significantly different from their performance on the posttest. The performance of learners in the non-ACE-SIMS group was significantly different from that of learners in the ACE-SIMS group. As a result, a significant difference in assessment scores of both groups proved the effectiveness of ACE-SIMS. The study found that in terms of reteaching the unmastered competency, ACE-SIMS has a "very acceptable" overall rating and thus aids in improving Grade 9 learners' academic performance on the identified least mastered competency. Moreover, it is recommended that Science teachers may use the developed ACE-SIMS as additional teaching material in teaching Earth Science; School administrators may provide learning opportunities for Science teachers such as seminars, Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions, and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) on how to develop their ACE-SIMS in their area of expertise so that there are still prepared materials for distance learning in the occurrence of an unexpected event; Learners may concentrate more on learning the newly developed ACE-SIMS in

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Earth Science to improve their academic performance; and Future researchers may develop ACE-SIMS that can work not only in android but also in other operating systems.

Keywords: Android-based Contextualized Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials, Quasi-experimental, Acceptability, Effectiveness.

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